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MICROEMULSION BASED GEL TECHNIQUE: - A NOVEL APPROACH FOR SUSTAINED DELIVERY TO TREAT FUNGAL INFECTION

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ABSTRACT

These modern days we have many problem and unsolved question about tablets and liquid preparation for treatment of chronic fungal diseases. To overcome all such problems semisolid preparations especially gels were came into picture. Gels are more prominent for delivering the drug to the site of action on skin. But the major problem with the gel is they are aqueous in nature and they cannot incorporate lipophilic drugs in them, and unfortunately most of the antifungal drugs are lipophilic in nature. So to solve the issue oil in water type emulsion is prepared. Then emulsion mixed with aqueous gel and a new drug delivery system emulgel is formed. The microemulgel is prepared by reducing the globule size of the emulsion (less then 200nm) so that drug particle can easily penetrate through the stratum corneum. In spite of penetration the microemulgel for skin has several other advantages like longer shelf-life, easily removable, self administration etc. It also has several favourable formulation advantages like easily spreadable, non grease, thixotropic, transparent, non-staining, and bio-friendly. This novel drug delivery system can use as targeted delivery for treatment of superficial fungal infection. The Novel vesicular drug delivery system also can be used for delivering analgesic, Anti-inflammatory, anti-acne, anti-viral drugs. This review gives detailed information about fungal diseases and their causative agents and properties, formulation consideration, various method of preparation, advantages, application and Characterization of microemulsion based gel for drug delivery system.

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INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections are now days one of the major problem for society. Fungal agents includes Tinea Pedis, Tinea Corporis, Tinea Capitis, Onychomycosis, Tinea Versicolor, Cutaneous Candidiasis and can cause serious diseases in human body or especially on human skin. Recently, there have been an increasing number of superficial fungal infections caused by fungi, such as those belonging to the genus Candida, Aspergillus, and Cryptococcus. The cases of suffering from bacterial, viral and fungal infections diseases are increases each year due to the ease of transmission from person to person. The incidences of fungal infection especially superficial fungal infections are increasing day by day and now days it covers more than 25% of the world's population. It has been estimated that more than 40 million people have suffering from fungal infections in developing and under developed nations. Proper, Targeted and effective treatment options are a necessity to avoid spreading the disease to peripheral organs and potential death ¹.

Topical drug delivery is a localized drug delivery system can be defined as delivery system which containing a drug preparations for the skin to treat skin disorders. The skin is the largest organ of the integumentary system and it making up 12– 15% of body weight and with a surface area of 1 – 2m². The skin is made up of seven layers of ectodermaltissue and guards the underlying muscles, bones, ligaments and internal organs. The molecules penetrate in the skin mainly by three routes: through intact stratum corneum, through sweat ducts, and through the sebaceous follicle. So for treatment of fungal disease on skin a topical formulation is very important.²

The topical drug can administered anywhere in the body through ophthalmic, rectal, vaginal and skin as topical routes. This drug delivery system is generally useful where the drug administration from other potent routes like oral, sublingual, rectal and parental are fails or not feasible like fungal infection. The Skin related or Dermatological products are diverse in formulation and range in consistency from liquid to semisolid to solid but the most popular and acceptable products are semisolid preparation. Within the major group of semisolid preparations, the use of aqueous gels has been increased both in cosmetics and in pharmaceutical preparations.³

The term Microemulsion is based on the size of the globules; due to their less size the drug particle easily particle can easily penetrate through stratum corneum and reach their site of action. The gel will hold the microemulsion for a longer period and it will help to release the drug in sustained manner.

Topical Delivery of Antifungal Drugs via Skin

The skin is a properly structured membrane and, it has basic three main layers, which are called as epidermis, dermis and hypodermis. Stratum corneum which is the extreme outer part of epidermis is mainly composed of dead and keratinized cells, and it is a wonderful barrier to penetration of drugs through the skin. Antifungal Drugs have to penetrate from the delivery system into skin layers to assure effective drug concentrations at the site of action. In topical drug administration, the drugs have prohibited or minimized enter into the systemic circulation to avoid the systemic adverse effects of drugs. The greatest challenge for topical antifungal drug delivery is permeate through the stratum corneum. To improve its permeability, new delivery approaches have been studied. Like Colloidal drug carriers such as microemulsions, vesicular carriers such as liposomes and, both lipidic and polymeric particulate carrier systems are one of those new carriers which ensure topical administration of antifungal drug.⁴

CLASSIFICATION OF TOPICAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM

Table 1:- Classification of topical formulations¹⁶

Liquid preparations	Semi-solid preparations	Solid preparations	Miscellaneous
Liniments	Ointments	Topical powders	Transdermal drug delivery system
Lotions	Creams	Poultices	Tapes and gauzes
Paints	Pastes	Plaster	Rubbing alcohols
Topical solution	Gels		Liquid cleaner
Topical tinctures	Poultices		Topical aerosols

Micro-emulgel

Topical microemulgel is formulated by adding suitable gelling agent to the optimized microemulsion formulation and therefore exhibit characteristics both of microemulsions and gels.

Microemulsions

Microemulsion system is a classic delivery system for most of the Antifungal drugs with objective of maximizing efficacy while minimizing toxicity. Microemulsion is thermodynamically stable transparent and translucent dispersions of oil and water which is stabilized by an interfacial film of surfactant and co-surfactant molecules and having the droplet size of 20-200 nm. In this system the interface is continuously and spontaneously fluctuating. Microemulsions as drug delivery tool show favourable properties like easy formation, optical isotropy, ability to be sterilized by filtration, high surface area (high solubilization capacity) and very small droplet size. This system has been widely studied in pharmaceuticals as drug delivery systems due to their capacity to solubilize hydrophobic drugs as well as their enhancement of topical and systemic availability. It shows very fast and very effective penetration to the skin. Maximum antifungal drugs such as Ketoconazole, Itraconazole, Fluconazole, Luliconazole, Clotrimazole, Econazole, Miconazole etc are lipophilic in nature for that reason it is very difficult to incorporate them in aqueous gel to gel localize benefits. So to overcome this problem, oil in water type microemulsion is formulate and incorporate in to aqueous gel. In this the drugs are incorporate in oil phase of emulsion and after applied to skin the drug will release for a long period of time.⁵

Advantages of Emulgel on the basis of patient compliance

1. Avoidance first pass metabolism in the body.
2. Systemic circulation is minimized or prevented.
3. Improve patient compliance and acceptability.
4. Suitable for self-medication.
5. Provide target drug delivery on the body.
6. Ability to easily terminate medication.
7. Can easily pass through skin having dual behavior i.e. hydrophobic as well as hydrophilic.
8. Very easy to apply on the hairy skin due to absence of greasiness and lack of residues upon application.

Advantages of using Emulgel as A DELIVERY System

- Lipophilic drugs can be easily mixed with aqueous gels using o/w emulsion.
- Better stability
- Better loading capacity
- Production feasibility and low preparation cost
- No intensive sonication
- Controlled release^{6,7}

Table2:- List of topical fungal infection and their treatment⁸⁻¹⁰

Fungal Infection	Common infective species	Affected site	Drugs for Treatment
Tinea pedis "athlete's foot"	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i>	Feet	1. Topical terbinafine 2. Topical imidazoles
Tinea capitis	<i>T. tonsurans</i>	Scalp	1. Topical terbinafine 2. Topical imidazoles
Tinea barbae	<i>Microsporum canis</i>	Beard	1. Terbinafine 2. Griseofulvin 3. Itraconazole
Tinea corporis "ring worm"	<i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i>	Skin other than bearded area, scalp, groin, hands or feet	1. Topical terbinafine 2. Topical imidazoles
Tinea cruris "jock itch"	<i>T. mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Scytalidium hyalinum</i> , <i>Candida albicans</i>	Groin, perineum and perianal areas	1. Topical terbinafine 2. Topical imidazoles
Tinea manuum	<i>Trichophyton rubrum</i> , <i>T. Mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Epidermophyton floccosum</i>	Hands	1. Topical terbinafine 2. Topical imidazoles
Pityriasis versicolor	<i>Pityrosporum orbiculare</i> , <i>P. ovale (Malassezia furfur)</i>	Back, Chest, Upper arms, neck and tummy	1. Selenium sulphide 2.5% lotion 2. Econazole 1% as a foaming solution 3. Itraconazole
Candidiasis	<i>C. albicans</i> , <i>C. glabrata</i> , <i>C.krusei</i> , <i>C. tropicalis</i> , <i>C. parapsilosis</i>	Skin and Nails	1. Imidazoles or Polyene e.g. Nystatin 2. Itraconazole
Onychomycosis	<i>T. rubrum</i> , <i>E. floccosum</i> , <i>T. mentagrophytes</i> , <i>Candida</i>	Nails	1. Itraconazole 2. Terbinafine

Rationale of emulgel as a topical drug delivery system

Various topical semisolid preparations are available to the market for restoring the fundamental function of the skin or pharmacologically alter an action to the underline tissue. Those formulations like ointment, cream and etc have several disadvantages like they are very sticky, lesser spreading coefficient, and more over they have problem with the stability. Because of these entire problems within the major group of semisolid preparations, only the transparent gels have expanded both in cosmetics and in pharmaceutical preparations.

A gel is a colloidal in nature that is 99% weight of liquid, which is deactivate by surface tension among it and a macromolecular network of fibres built from a small amount of a gelatin substance present. It rubbed onto the skin for delivering the pain medication and infection fighting drugs to an affected site of the body. New technologies now allow other drugs to be penetrating through the skin. These can be helpful to treat not just the affected areas but the whole body and these can be applied to hairy skin without any uncomfortable feelings.^{2, 11, 12}

FORMULATION OF EMULGEL:- IMPORTANT CONSTITUENTS OF EMULGEL PREPARATION

Drug: -

Various physicochemical and biological properties of drugs given for topical or transdermal delivery are applicable for selection of drug for emulgel. The anti fungal drugs especially in the Azoles and imidazole classes of drugs like Itraconazole, Ketoconazole, Fluconazole and etc are selected for formulation of topical antifungal emulgel.

Vehicle: -

The vehicle is an important link between potency and therapeutic effectiveness of the drug, since substantial research in Pharmaceuticals has shown that the composition of the vehicle can greatly impact the rate and extent of absorption (bioavailability). In the formulation of dermatologic vehicles that maximize bioavailability, two factors are most crucial: solubilizing the drug in vehicle and maximizing movement (partitioning) of drug from vehicle to stratum corneum.

The vehicle has following properties:

- The vehicle should efficiently deposit the drug on the skin with proper distribution.
- The vehicle should release the drug to
- It should show targeted delivery of the drug to the site of action.
- To provide a pharmacologic effect.
- Cosmetically acceptable to the patient. It should provide a smooth appearance to the application site.
- Due to the high efficiency of the epidermal barrier, the amount of topical drug that gets through the stratum corneum is generally low. Rate and extent of absorption vary depending on characteristics of the vehicle but is also influenced by the active agent itself.¹¹

Aqueous Material:

These materials are used to form the aqueous phase of the emulsion. The aqueous phase may contain hydrophilic agents and various preservatives. Commonly used agents are water, alcohol. The water is also used in the formulation of gel.¹¹⁻¹²

Oils:

Various oils are used in the formation of oily phase of the emulsion. The oil phase has great importance in the formulation of emulsion /microemulsion/ nanoemulsion as this physicochemical properties of oil significantly regulate the spontaneity of the emulsification /micro- emulsification / nano emulsification process, the size of droplet of the emulsion and the solubility of the drug. The oil, which will show the highest solubility potential for the specific drug candidate, is preferred as an oily phase for the formulation of emulsion/ microemulsion. This will help to ensure the maximal loading of the drug. Hence, the choice of the oily phase is often a compromise between its tendency to solubilize the drug and its capability to facilitate the formation of the respective emulsion with desired characteristics. Oil phases which are used in development of emulgel are light liquid paraffin, balsam oil, birch oil, castor oil, isopropyl myristate, myrrh oil, rose hip oil, wheat germ oil, Isopropyl stearate, Isopropyl palmitate and etc. Recent trend is towards use of semi-synthetic oils which are more stable than their natural counterparts. Poorly aqueous soluble drugs need to have good solubility in dispersed oil phase to form efficient o/w microemulsion system. Even the greater quantity of oil content in o/w microemulsion can increase the size of droplets.

For externally applied emulsions, mineral oils, either alone or combined with soft or hard paraffin, are widely used both as the vehicle for the drug and for their occlusive and sensory characteristics.¹²⁻¹⁴

Table 3:- The uses of different types of oil with their quantity (in percentage)¹³⁻¹⁵

Sl no.	Oil	Dosage form
1)	Ethyl Oleate	Emulsion
2)	Mineral oil	Emulsion
3)	Oleic acid	Emulsion
4)	Vegetable oils	Emulsion
4a)	coconut oil, & olive oil	Emulsion
4b)	sunflower oil	Emulsion
4c)	soyabean oil	Emulsion
5)	Light Liquid Paraffin	Emulsion & Emulgel
6)	Isopropyl myristate	Emulsion
7)	Isopropyl palmitate	Emulsion
8)	Propylene Glycol	Gel

Emulsifiers

Emulsifying agent mainly consists of surfactant and co-surfactant; their concentration should be used in different proportion. In the formation of microemulsion the surfactant may be ionic or non-ionic, which determines the stabilizing interactions of the hydrophilic end of the surfactant with the aqueous phase. The main use of emulsifiers is to control the emulsification process and provide a definite stability to the emulsion because emulsifiers are thermodynamically unstable. The single-chain surfactants alone are inadequate to reduce the interfacial tension sufficiently to enable a microemulsion to form. So, the co-surfactants are applied, which provide the interfacial film appropriate flexibility to take up various curvatures required to form microemulsion over a wide range of composition. These agents are used to promote emulsification during manufacture and control its stability during a shelf life that can vary from days to months or years for commercial preparations.¹⁶⁻¹⁷

Table 4:- Examples of Surfactants and co-surfactants generally used in Microemulsion preparation¹⁶⁻¹⁷

Surfactant	Co-surfactant
Polysorbate (tween 80 and tween 20)	Sorbitan monooleate (Span 80)
Lecithins	Sorbitan monostearate,
Decylpolyglucoside (Labrafil M 1944 LS),	Propylene glycol,
Polyglyceryl-6-diolate (PlurolOleique,	Propylene glycol monocaprylate (Capryol 90),
Diocetyl sodium	2-(2-ethoxyethoxy) ethanol (Transcutol P)

Permeation enhancer: -

Penetration enhancers are the substances that help the absorption of the formulation through the skin. This ingredients are temporarily disrupts the skin barrier, fluidize the lipid channels between coenocytes, alter the partitioning of the drug into skin structures, or otherwise enhance delivery into skin. Ideally, these substances should be pharmacologically inert, nonirritating, nontoxic, and compatible with the excipients and drugs, colourless, odourless, tasteless, and inexpensive and have good solvent properties.¹⁸⁻¹⁹

Mechanism of penetration enhancers

Penetration enhancers may act by one or more of these main mechanisms:

1. Highly ordered structure of stratum corneum lipid disruption.
2. Proper interaction with intercellular protein.
3. Help to improved the partition of the drug, co-enhancer, or solvent into the stratum corneum.¹¹

Table 5:- Quantity and use of Penetration enhancers¹⁸⁻¹⁹

Penetration Enhancer	Quantity (%)	Dosage Form
Oleic acid	1	Gel
Lecithin	5	Gel
Urea	10	Gel
Linoleic acid	5	Gel
Clove oil	8	Emulgel
Menthol	5	Emulgel
Isopropyl myristate	5	Gel
Cinnamon	8	Emulgel

Gelling Agent: -

The gelling agents are used to increase the viscosity of the liquid formulation without changing other properties. These agents are used to improve the consistency dosage forms and also be used as thickening agent. These agents are mainly used to form aqueous gel base which when add with emulsion form emulgel.¹⁸

Table 6: - Use of gelling agents¹⁸⁻¹⁹

Gelling Agents	Quantity (%)	Dosage form
Carbopol-934	1-1.5	Emulgel
Carbopol-940	1-1.5	Emulgel
HPMC K100M	1-1.5	Emulgel
HPMC-2910	2.5	Emulgel
HPMC	3.5	Gel
Sodium CMC	1	Gel
Poloxamer 407	1	Gel
Combination of HPMC & Carbopol	1.2-1.5	Emulgel

Formulation of Emulgel: -

There are various methods to formulate emulgel by using different ingredients.

First step includes formation of Microemulsion and then add the microemulsion in aqueous gel base to form appropriate Microemulgel.

The first method of preparation of emulgel was reported on the research work of Mohammad et al. (2004) with minor modification. In this method the aqueous gel phase was prepared by incorporation of sufficient quantity of gelling agent in water and soaks for overnight. Then the pH was adjusted to 6 to 6.5 using Triethanolamine (TEA). Oily phase of microemulsion was prepared by dissolving span 20 in light liquid paraffin. Aqueous phase of emulsion was prepared by dissolving tween 20 in purified water, then propylene glycol solution was prepared by dissolving methyl paraben and propyl paraben in propylene glycol and then antifungal drug was dissolve in ethanol and both the solution are added to aqueous phase. Then both of oily and aqueous phase were heated at 70–80 °C, after this both the phases are mixed with constant stirring until cooled to room temperature. When both the components both emulsions & gel get ready then the Emulgel is prepared by mixing emulsion with gel in 1:1 ratio with gentle stirring.^{17, 20} Shahin et al. (2011) followed a different method to develop Emulgel for Clotrimazole delivery.

In this method oily phase was prepared by dissolving drug and span 60 in jojoba oil with the aid of magnetic stirrer at 75 °C after that subsequent cooling was provided followed by addition of Carbopol to the oily phase. In second step aqueous phase is prepared by dissolving Brij35 in propylene glycol. After that in final step oily phase was added to the aqueous phase and following their emulsification using the over head mixer for 10 min at 1400 rpm, and then introduced emulsion into the homogenizer for 5 min at 10,000 rpm. Gellification of emulsion involves addition of gelling agent, triethanolamine (formulae containing Carbopol either alone or in combination) and/or HPMC to the emulsion using over head mixer at 200 rpm for 45 min thereby adjusting the pH of formulation containing Carbopol to 5.5–6.5 using triethanolamine.

And in other process Dickinson Eric et al. (2012) prepared a solid-like emulsion gel from a stable liquid-like emulsion by gelling the continuous phase or aggregating the emulsion droplets. Even simply forcing all the droplets closer together by centrifugation can be sufficient to produce a concentrated protein-stabilized emulsion with gel-like behaviour, i.e., elasticity at small deformations.^{6, 20}

CHARACTERIZATION OF EMULGELS**Physical Examination: -**

The prepared emulgel were inspected visually for their colour, Grittiness, odour, texture, homogeneity and Consistency.

Determination of pH

The pH of the formulation was determined using digital pH meter. The digital pH meter electrode was washed by distilled water and then dipped into the formulation to measure pH. The 1gm of prepared emulgel was dissolved in distilled water and made up the volume up to 100ml with distilled water and keep aside for 2 hours to prepare 1% of emulgel solution and then check the pH. The test is carried in triplicate and the mean was calculated.^{21, 22}

Percentage yield

The empty tube was Weighed in which the gel formulation was stored then again the tube was weighed with gel formulation. Then the weight of empty tube was subtracted with the weight of tube contain gel formulation then it gave the practical yield. Then the percentage yield was calculated by the formula.²³

Rheological study

The viscosity of the optimized batches was calculated using Brookfield viscometer with spindle no. 7, which is mainly use for gel formulations. The assembly was connected to a thermostatically controlled circulating water bath maintained temperature 25 °C. The gel formulation whose viscosity was determined by adding the gel into a beaker covered with thermostatic jacket. The Spindle was allowed to move freely in the emulgel and the viscosity was noted at different rpm along with torque value.²⁴

Zeta Potential Determination

The zeta potential of the formulation assessed by laser Doppler anemometry using Zeta Sizer. The sample was diluted with distilled water (1:100 v/v) before analysis and mixed for one minute using vertex mixer.²⁵

Drug content determination

The drug content of micro-emulgel was measured by a process where, known quantity of the emulgel formulation (one gram) was dissolve in suitable solvent by sonication. Then proper dilutions were made and the final solution was filtered to obtain clear solution. Absorbance was determined using UV- spectrophotometer. Then a standard plot of drug was prepared in the same solvent. Drug content was calculated using the standard plot by putting the absorbance reading. The process was performed thrice.^{17, 26}

The formula use:-

$$\text{Drug Content} = (\text{Concentration of drug} \times \text{Dilution Factor} \times \text{Volume taken}) \times \text{Conversion Factor}$$

Spreadability

Spreadability or Spreading co-efficient was determined by such equipment which is designed and transformed for laboratory use. It made up of a solid piece of wood, which is provided by a lifter at one end. By this method, Spreadability was measured on the basis of "Slip" and "Drag" feature of emulgels. A first glass slide was attached on the wooden piece. An extra amount of emulgel (quantity- 2g) was uniformly spread on this glass slide. The emulgel formulation was placed between the first glass slide and second glass slide having same diameter as that of the fixed first slide. The second glass slide is attached with the hook. Weight of 500 mg was put on the top of the two slides for 5 min to remove air and to provide a proper uniform film of the emulgel between the two slides. Sufficient quantity of weight bars was placed in the pan attached to the pulley with the help of hook. At that side where weight was applied, the time taken for the upper slide to move the distance and separate away from the other slide (lower) was noted. The experiment was done in triplicate and the mean of such determinations was calculated for each formulation.^{23, 27, 28}

Spreadability was measured by following formulation:

$$S = M \cdot L / T$$

Where,

S = Spreadability.

M = Weight tied to upper slide.

L = Length of glass slides.

T = Time taken to separate the slides completely from each other

Spreadability was calculated to designate the particular size of area to which gel was easily spread on the implementation to skin or disease site. The spreadability was also one of the main criteria on which therapeutic effectiveness of the formulation base on.²⁹

Swelling Index

Swelling of the polymer was based on the concentration of the polymer, ionic strength and the presence of water. To calculate the swelling index of optimized topical emulgel formulation, 1 gm of emulgel is kept on porous aluminum foil and then placed aside in a 50 ml beaker containing 10 ml 0.1 N NaOH . Then samples were withdrawn from beakers at specific time intervals and placed it on dry area for specific time, after this reweighed the sample.^{30, 31}

Swelling index is determined by a formula:

$$\text{Swelling Index (SW) \%} = [(W_t - W_0) / W_0] \times 100.$$

Where, (SW) % = Equilibrium percent swelling,

W_0 = Original weight of emulgel at zero time

W_t = Weight of swollen emulgel after time t

Extrudability study

It was a standard surveillance test done to calculate amount of force needed to release the gel completely from the tube. The method was applied for calculation of applied shear in the area of the rheogram parallel to a shear rate distinctly the yield value and demonstrates consequent plug flow. In the present study the process taken for evaluation of emulgel formulation for extrudability was based upon the sum in rate of emulgel i.e., quantity of percentage of emulgel and emulgel released from lacquered aluminum collapsible tube on application of weight in grams required extrude more than 0.5 cm part of emulgel in 10 seconds. More amounts was extrude from the tube better was the extrudability. The calculation of extrudability of emulgel formulation must be done three times and the value was presented.³²

The extrudability was determined using the formula:

$$\text{Extrudability} = \text{Applied weight to expel emulgel from tube (in gm)} / \text{Area (in cm}^2\text{)}$$

Globule size and its distribution in emulgel

Globule size and distribution was performed by Malvern Zetasizer. A 1 gm quantity of sample was dissolved in distilled water and shaken vigorously to get uniform dispersion. Then sample was added to photocell of Zetasizer to get mean globule diameter and distribution.³⁴

Bio-adhesive strength measurement

A modified balance strategy was applied for determination of bioadhesion of emulgel formulation. Fresh goat hairless skin was obtained from a local slaughter – house and used within 2 hours of slaughter. The membrane was washed with distilled water and then with 0.1 N NaOH. Then the skin was cut into two pieces.

The two pans were separated from physical balance. On the left side, a glass slide was placed and a 100 ml beaker was attached on right side pan. A weight of 20 g was placed on the left side, for balancing the assembly. Another glass slide was hanged below the above slide. The two pieces of goat skin was attached with the glass slides separately. One gram of gel was applied between two goat skin faces. Proper bioadhesion bond was formed by applying a little pressure, and then slowly water was poured to right side beaker, till the emulgel was detached from one face of rat skin. The water volume was converted to mass. This gave the bioadhesive strength of gel in grams.^{34, 35}

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) study

The surface morphology of the Emulgel formulation was determined by using scanning electron microscope by gold sputter technique. The system was vacuum dried, coated with gold palladium, and observed microscopically.³⁶

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM)

The emulgel formulation after hydration was established by Transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Samples were prepared by dissolving emulgel to phosphate buffer (pH 5.5) by shaking the mixture manually for 1 minute. Then a drop of the sample was put on a carbon-coated copper grid after 15 minutes and negatively stained with 1% aqueous solution of phosphotungstic acid. The grid was allowed to air dry thoroughly and samples were viewed on a TEM.^{18, 37}

In-vitro release/permeation studies

The in-vitro release rates of prepared microemulsion based gel were calculated to evaluate the effects of the formulation factors. The diffusion test was performed using Franz diffusion cells fabricated locally with dialysis membrane pore size: 0.2 mm at 37 ± 0.1 °C and egg membrane at same temperature.

The beaker was filled with specific quantity of phosphate buffer pH 5.5 which acts as receptor fluid. The receptor fluid was continuously stirred by externally driven magnetic beads and the diffusion cell was placed on magnetic stirrer. The temperature of the receptor fluid was maintained at 37° C. Specific quantity microemulsion based gel was placed in the cylindrical hollow tube which acts as donor compartment, one end of which sealed by dialysis membrane of pore size: 0.2 mm or with egg membrane. The sample (5ml liquid) was collected at suitable time intervals. The volume of fluid which was withdrawn for analysis is replaced with the same volume of the freshly prepared buffer solution after each sampling. The sample was analyzed by UV-Visible spectrophotometer at a suitable wavelength after proper dilutions with suitable solvent. Cumulative corrections were made to get the total amount of drug release at each time interval.^{38, 39}

Drug release kinetic study

To analyze the mechanism of drug release from the topical emulgel, the release data should be fitted to following equations: -

$$\text{Zero – order equation: } Q = k_0 t$$

Where Q is the amount of drug released at time t, and k_0 is the zero – order release rate.

$$\text{First – order equation: } \ln(100 - Q) = \ln 100 - k_1 t$$

Where Q is the percent of drug release at time t, and k_1 is the first – order release rate constant.

$$\text{Higuchi's equation: } Q = k_2 \sqrt{t}$$

Where Q is the percent of drug release at time t, and k_2 is the diffusion rate constant.⁴⁰

Microbiological assay

The method used for microbiological assay is named as Ditch plate technique. It was an approach used for evaluation of fungistatic activity of a compound. It is mainly applied for semisolid formulations. In this previously prepared Sabouraud's agar dried plates are used. Specific quantity (3 grams) of the Gellified emulsion was placed in a ditch cut in the plate. Freshly prepared culture loops were covered across the agar at a right angle from the ditch to the edge of the plate. After incubation for 18 to 24 hours at 25°C, the fungal growth is observed and the percentage inhibition is measured as follows.⁴¹

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = L_2 / L_1 \times 100$$

Where,

L_1 = total length of the streaked culture

L2 =length of inhibition

Skin irritation test

The specific quantity of microemulsion based gel preparation was applied to properly shaven skin of experimental rats. The sample was applied through double gauze layer to an area of skin approximately 1" x 1" (2.54 x 2.54 cm²). Its adverse effect like change in skin colour and change in skin morphology should be monitored up to 24 hours. The total quantity of 8 rats can be used of the study. If no irritation occurs on the skin of the rats then the test is passed. If the any symptom of irritation occurs in more than 2 rats, then the study should be repeated.^{42, 43}

Stability studies

The optimized microemulgel formulation are packed in aluminium collapsible tubes with the quantity of 5 gm and subjected to stability studies at 25°C/60% RH, 30°C/65% RH, and 40°C/75% RH for a period of 3 months. Samples are check in every 15-day time intervals and evaluated on the basis of physical appearance, pH, viscosity, drug content, and In-vitro drug release profile.^{44, 45}

Table 7: Some marketed preparations of emulgel with their brand and company names^{14, 33, 46}

SL No.	Product Name	Drug	Manufacturer
1)	Miconaz-Hemulgel	Miconazole nitrate, Hydrocortisone	Medical union Pharmaceuticals
2)	Voltarenemulgel	Diclofenac diethyl ammonium	Novartis Pharma
3)	Clinagel	Clindamycin phosphate Allantoin	Stiefel Pharma
4)	Excec gel	Clindamycin, Adapalene	Zee Laboratories
5)	Topinate gel	Clobetasol propionate	Systopic Pharma
6)	Zorotene gel	Tezaratene	Elder Pharmaceuticals
7)	Avindo gel	Azithromycin	Cosme Pharma Lab.
8)	Acent gel	Aceclofenac	Intra Labs India Pvt. Ltd
9)	Nadicin cream	Nadifloxacin	Psycho remedies
10)	Cloben gel	Clotrimazole, Beclomethasone	Indoco Remedies

CONCLUSION

The microemulsion based gel is very good drug delivery system for delivering hydrophobic drugs. The main antifungal drugs like azoles and imidazoles are mainly lipophilic in nature for that it is very difficult to incorporate them into an aqueous gel. To solve that microemulsion came into picture. Lipophilic drugs can be easily incorporate in the oil droplets of o/w microemulsion and then added to aqueous gel for preparation of final emulgel formulation. This microemulsion based gel can also act as depot of drug, which will release drug in controlled manner at the targeted site for that reason this system, could be formulation of choice in many dermatological diseases. Microemulgel formulation can be applied for controlling the release rate of drugs which have short half-life. Microemulgel is helpful in enhancing Spreadability, adhesion, viscosity and extrusion of the gel formulation. Currently, very few marketed microemulsion based gel formulation are available in market. But this formulation has very good potential on it especially for antifungal drugs and more over it is very much patient friendly, so we can see that in recent years there will be more microemulgel formulations in the market.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Nil

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

ITZ: - Itraconazole

nm: - Nano-meter

TEA: - Triethanolamine

SEM: - Scanning Electron Microscopy

TEM: - Transmission Electron Microscopy

O/W: - Oil in Water

Gm/gm: - Gram

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